

RCPL-32 and RCPL-3-6: two promising rice lines for the mid-hills of Sikkim, India

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Rice is the second most important crop in Sikkim, India covering about 19,000 ha. Yields average 1.3 t ha⁻¹. In Sikkim, rice is cultivated on terraces using gravity flow water. Commonly grown local cultivars (Attey, Chirkey, Krishnabhog, Tapre, Kalonunia, Tulasi, Champasare, and Bhuinphool) are late-maturing, tall, and low-tillering. Their yields are poor but they have good quality attributes. Suitable substitutes for these cultivars must be semi-tall, medium-maturing, nonlodging, have low photoperiod sensitivity, high yield potential, and good quality. After 4 yr of evaluation, lines RCPL-3-2 and RCPL-3-6 outyielded all other lines and checks (Table 1).

RCPL-3-2, a selection from cross Moirangphou/Jaya, is semidwarf (98-105 cm), while RCPL-3-6, a selection from cross CH-988/IR24, is also semidwarf but slightly taller. RCPL-3-2 is nonglutinous, whereas RCPL-3-6 is a semiglutinous rice. Both are medium in maturity and resistant

Toag92: a shortduration rice cultivar for Turkey

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Toag92, a rice variety derived from the cross Nucleoryza/Labela, was released in 1992. The main aim of the breeding program was to create a variety that does well in the second cropping season in the Aegean and Mediterranean regions of Turkey. Toag92, however, also has high yields in northern Turkey, where it did particularly well when sown late and in areas where existing varieties cannot be grown because of their long vegetative

Table 1. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) of promising lines and checks over years and locations in Sikkim, India.

Location	Year	RCPL-3-2	RCPL-3-6	DR-92	Attey
Tadong	1990	5.0	4.3	3.8	2.0
Tadong	1991	5.0	4.5	2.9	1.2
Tadong	1992	4.1	4.6	2.5	1.3
Tadong	1993	4.3	4.4	3.0	1.8
Tadong	1994	4.2	4.4	3.6	1.4
Pakyong	1992	4.0	4.6	3.3	1.9
Pakyong	1993	3.9	3.5	2.6	2.2
Dharmdin	1992	6.0	5.5	3.8	2.2
Nazitam	1992	4.9	4.6	3.5	2.1
Nazitam	1993	4.9	4.6	3.2	2.0

Table 2. Important characteristics of RCPL-3-2 and RCPL-3-6.

Characteristic	RCPL-3-2	RCPL-3-6
Plant height (cm)	98-105	110-115
Days to flowering	60-70	67-72
Days to maturity	115-120	120-125
Ear-bearing tillers (no.)	9-15	8-14
Panicle length (cm)	20-23	25-27
Flag leaf	Erect	Erect
Awn type	Awnless	Awnless
Husk grain color	Straw	Straw
Kernel color	Dull	Dull
1,000-grain weight (g)	25.4	23.5
Grain length (cm)	0.83	0.84
Grain width (cm)	0.30	0.28
L-B ratio	2.77	2.94
Endosperm type	Nonglutinous	Semiglutinous
Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	4.5-5.0	4.2-4.6
Reaction to leaf blast (0-9 scale)	0-2	0-2
Reaction to neck blast (%)	0-1	0-1

to lodging, leaf and neck blast. Distinguishing traits for both include panicle length, 1,000-grain weight, L-B ratio, panicle-bearing tillers, and endosperm type (Table 2).

RCPL-3-2 and RCPL-3-6 are suitable for early sowing, and will enable farmers to adopt more profitable rice-based cropping systems such as rice-mustard/pea/barley, that promise to increase cropping intensity under rainfed conditions. ■

Table 1. Comparison of some agronomic characters of Toag92 and commercial varieties. Bornova, Turkey (3-yr av).

Variety	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Height (cm)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Yield (kg d ⁻¹)	Duration (d)	Sterility (%)	Leaf blast ^a
Toag 92	5.3	64	33	5.95	89	16	0
Baldo	4.1	92	38	3.66	112	24	-
Ribe	4.5	99	33	4.24	106	30	8
Krasnodorsky 424	4.4	101	31	4.40	100	24	4

^aScored using the *Standard evaluation system* (SES) 0-9 scale where 0 = highly resistant and 9 = highly susceptible.

durations. Toag92 matures 2 wk earlier than Ribe.

Its low sterility under Mediterranean conditions makes it promising for the southeastern Anatolia region, where August temperatures are quite high.

Toag92 is of medium height (88 cm), 30 cm shorter than Ribe, and is resistant to lodging. The yield d⁻¹ of Toag92 is almost 50% more than that of other improved cultivars. Toag92 is also resistant to leaf blast (Table 1).

Toag92 has medium grain and is free of white belly. Quality is good and similar to that of Baldo, Ribe, and Krasnodorsky-424 (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Quality traits of Toag92. Bornova, Turkey.

Variety	Amylose content (%)	Protein content (%)	KOH reaction	White belly ^a
Toag92	18.8	13.7	Low	5
Baldo	16.8	9.8	Low	0
Ribe	15.6	7.8	Low	-
Krasnodorsky 424	-	7.4	Low	5

^aScored using the SES scale where 0 = no belly. 9 = more than 20% of kernel area.

KK1536-C: a modern high-yielding rice variety for irrigated lowlands in Papua New Guinea

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Out of 122 genotypes we evaluated in 1991, KK15-36-C (IR 5657-33-2/BKNDR1031-7, Nepalese in origin) performed the best

and was selected as one of six genotypes for further evaluation.

We confirmed the high yield potential (10.5 t ha⁻¹) of KK15-36-C in local and regional yield trials conducted during 1992-95. At the OISCA Farm in Kokopo, Rabaul, KK15-36-C and Ayung yielded the most of the varieties tested. At Bubia during 1991 and 1995, the variety was either highest yielding (6-7 t ha⁻¹ during 1994, 9.5 t ha⁻¹ during 1995) or at par with the highest yielding genotypes.

The variety is semidwarf (<110 cm) with medium-tillering ability. It has long (>25 cm), fully filled panicles with more than 100 grains panicle⁻¹. The 1,000-grain weight is 30 g. Its foliage remains green up to late maturity.

The variety's grains are long and medium bold, awned and translucent. The milling recovery is very good. KK 15-36-C is extremely well suited for general cultivation in the irrigated lowland fields of Papua New Guinea. ■

Birsa Dhan 201 and Birsa Dhan 202: early-maturing varieties for Bihar, India

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Birsa Dhan 201 was developed by crossing TN1/Brown Gora 23-19, and Birsa Dhan 202 by crossing Jaya/BR34. Both varieties were released during 1985 and re-released in 1995 for use in the Chotanagpur and Santhal Parganas region of Bihar, India. Birsa Dhan 201 is an early-duration variety that matures in 105-110 d under transplanting. It is nonlodging, nonshattering, and highly responsive to chemical fertilizers, yielding 3.0-3.5 t ha⁻¹. It has compact, long panicles with bold grains and white kernels. It is moderately resistant to

Performance of Birsa Dhan 202 in the All-India coordinated trials. 1989 and 1990.

Variety	Mean of different locations			
	1989		1990	
	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Days to 50% flowering	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Days to 50% flowering
Birsa Dhan 202	6.3	101	3.5	94
Vikas	6.1	99	-	-
Ratna	6.1	95	-	-
Rasi	-	-	2.6	85
Local (control)	6.2	99	3.1	92

blast, bacterial leaf blight, stem borer, and gall midge.

Birsa Dhan 202 is intermediate in plant type and provides adequate rice straw for cattle feed, as required by farmers in the region. The variety has very good seedling vigor and produces heavy, drooping panicles. It is stiff-strawed, making it resistant to lodging. The grains are long and bold. producing white kernels. It is moderately

resistant to blast, stem borer, and bacterial leaf blight, but moderately susceptible to gall midge. The variety yields reasonably well, producing 5-6 t ha⁻¹ when 40-60 kg N ha⁻¹ is applied (see table). A lot of this region has been planted to Birsa Dhan 202. Farmers have been sharing its seed with each other, increasing the area planted to it.

Both varieties have acceptable taste. and grain and cooking quality.